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OPTIMIZING SCIENCE EDUCATION: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON THE EFFICACY OF INTENSIVE SCAFFOLDING STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCED LEARNER ASSESSMENT PERFORMANCE

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 caused major disruptions in education, forcing schools to adopt distance learning modalities that limited student engagement and widened learning gaps, especially in Science. As in-person classes resumed, teachers at Santa Cruz Integrated National High School – Gatid Extension observed that many Grade 7 students continued to struggle in mastering basic Science concepts due to the shift in learning environments. These challenges reflected the 2022 PISA results, which showed that Filipino students performed below global standards in Science literacy. To address this, the study examined the effectiveness of intensive scaffolding strategies in improving Science performance among Grade 7 students who scored below 80% during the first two quarters of the school year 2022–2023. Scaffolding, a structured instructional support designed to aid learners toward mastery, was utilized to strengthen comprehension, critical thinking, and engagement in Science lessons.

Methods

The study employed a quantitative, quasi-experimental design with pre- and post-assessments to measure the effects of intensive scaffolding on student performance. Forty Grade 7 students were selected through stratified sampling from two sections based on low Science scores. Weekly lessons incorporated scaffolding techniques such as guided questioning, modeling, and re-teaching. Each session began with a pre-assessment and ended with a post-assessment to track learning progress. The research instruments included two 40-item tests aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) for the third and fourth quarters. Data were collected from March to June 2023 and analyzed using standard deviation and t-tests for two dependent means to determine statistical significance between pre- and post-test results.

Results and Discussion

Results showed significant improvement in students' Science performance after the application of scaffolding strategies. In the third quarter, the mean score increased from 12.30 (MPS = 30.75) in the pre-assessment to 25.53 (MPS = 63.81) post-intervention, producing a t-value of 15.83 ($p = 0.00001$). Likewise, in the fourth quarter, scores rose from 15.45 (MPS = 38.63) to 27.28 (MPS = 68.19), with a t-value of 11.11 ($p = 0.00001$). Both results were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), confirming that the improvements were attributed to the scaffolding intervention. These findings are consistent with Pereira and Lopes (2021) and Tabib (2022), who reported that scaffolding promotes deeper comprehension and higher achievement through structured support.

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